

Bridging the Cybersecurity
Awareness Gap: A
Communication-First
Approach

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Abstract

This white paper examines **cybersecurity awareness as a communication challenge and a key component of cyber resilience**. It explores how people understand, interpret, and respond to cyber risks, and why awareness strategies need to reflect real decision-making contexts.

The paper focuses on three areas: **the human factors** that make individuals vulnerable to manipulation, **the design of targeted awareness campaigns**, and the **use of engaging formats** such as gamification, storytelling, simulations, and team-based activities. It highlights the limits of generic and fear-based communication, the importance of audience segmentation, and the role of leadership, SMEs, and measurement in building stronger awareness practices.

Developed within the framework of [COcyber](#), the paper **supports a communication-focused approach to cybersecurity awareness** and contributes to wider efforts to strengthen cybersecurity culture in Europe.

Keywords

Cybersecurity awareness, cybersecurity communication, cyber resilience, social engineering, behavioural cybersecurity, audience segmentation, gamification, storytelling, cybersecurity culture, SMEs, organisational awareness, cyber risk communication, cybersecurity training, human factors, cyber threats

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Executive Summary

This white paper has been developed within the framework of the [COcyber project](#) (Coordination between the Cybersecurity Civilian and Defence Spheres), a European initiative dedicated to strengthening exchange, coordination, and collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity communities. Through knowledge sharing, cross-sector dialogue, and the promotion of common approaches, COcyber seeks to contribute to a **stronger and more resilient European cybersecurity ecosystem**.

In line with these objectives, this white paper presents **cybersecurity awareness as a strategic communication function** and a core element of cyber resilience. In Europe, cyber incidents continue to rise alongside stronger regulation and growing investment in technical defences. This points to the need for awareness strategies that help people understand risks, recognise their role, and act with confidence when cyber threats appear.

The paper examines the human factor as both a vulnerability and a strategic point of intervention. People are targeted because attackers can often influence behaviour faster than they can exploit technical systems. Social engineering, urgency, authority, familiarity, and contextual credibility all shape how individuals make decisions under pressure. Effective awareness must therefore reflect real decision-making conditions, different audiences, and the organisational contexts in which cyber risks emerge.

The paper also highlights the limits of generic and fear-based campaigns. **Strong awareness strategies** require clear objectives, audience segmentation, practical guidance, leadership engagement, and systematic measurement. SMEs require particular attention, as limited time, resources, and expertise shape how awareness can be implemented in practice.

Finally, the paper explores creative and participatory formats such as **gamification, storytelling, simulations, and team-based exercises**. These approaches can

strengthen attention, retention, and practical understanding when they are well designed and aligned with communication objectives.

Overall, the white paper calls for a shift from awareness as *information delivery* to awareness as *behaviour-focused communication*. For COcyber, this means supporting shared learning between civilian and defence cybersecurity communities and contributing to a European cybersecurity culture built through communication, participation, and collective responsibility.

Introduction

Europe is facing a cybersecurity paradox. Threats are increasing, investments are rising, and regulatory frameworks are becoming more robust, yet cyber incidents continue to grow in both frequency and impact. Recent figures from ENISA indicate that more than 11,000 cybersecurity incidents were recorded across the European Union between June 2023 and July 2024, including hundreds of coordinated attacks affecting multiple Member States (1). At the same time, organizational spending on information security has expanded significantly, with cybersecurity representing an increasing share of overall IT budgets and median expenditure doubling within a short period (2).

Despite these developments, the overall effectiveness of cybersecurity efforts remains uneven. The continued prevalence of successful incidents suggests that technical investment alone is not sufficient to address the evolving threat landscape. While robust infrastructure, advanced tools, and regulatory compliance are essential components of cybersecurity, they do not fully account for how risks materialise in practice.

A substantial proportion of cybersecurity incidents are closely linked to human behaviour. Errors in judgment, limited awareness, misinterpretation of risk, and susceptibility to manipulation techniques such as phishing and other forms of social engineering continue to play a central role in incident occurrence (3). These behaviours do not arise in isolation but are shaped by organisational context, communication practices, and the conditions under which individuals are required to make decisions. As a result, cybersecurity outcomes depend not only on the resilience of systems but also on how individuals understand, interpret, and respond to cyber risk.

This has direct implications for how cybersecurity strategies are designed. Awareness and communication are often treated as secondary or supporting functions, typically addressed through standardised training programmes or broad information campaigns. However, evidence indicates that approaches based primarily on information dissemination or compliance-driven messaging have limited impact on behaviour, particularly when applied uniformly across diverse audiences with different roles, levels of expertise, and operational environments (5)(6).

At the policy level, the importance of awareness has been formally recognised. The NIS2 Directive requires Member States to incorporate cybersecurity education and awareness into national strategies, reflecting an understanding that resilience depends on both technical and human factors (7). At the same time, available data suggests that while

investment in technology continues to grow, attention to the human dimension remains inconsistent. In some sectors, awareness of regulatory obligations remains limited, and the proportion of personnel dedicated to cybersecurity functions has not increased at the same pace as overall spending (2).

These dynamics point to a structural gap between policy ambition, technical capability, and behavioural outcomes. Addressing this gap requires a more integrated approach in which communication is positioned as a core component to cybersecurity. This involves moving beyond generic awareness efforts towards communication strategies that are informed by behavioural insights, adapted to specific audiences, and designed to support decision-making in operational contexts.

Developed within the framework of the [COcyber](#) project, this white paper examines **how communication can contribute to more effective cybersecurity practices**, particularly at the intersection of behavioural factors, organisational context, and awareness strategy. It is structured around three complementary dimensions. First, it looks at the human factors that shape how people perceive, interpret, and respond to cyber risks. Second, it focuses on the design of awareness strategies, showing why effective communication requires audience segmentation, clear objectives, and measurable outcomes. Third, it explores how creative and interactive formats can make cybersecurity more engaging and actionable.

1. Understanding the human factor in cybersecurity communication

Cybersecurity risks materialise not only through technical vulnerabilities, but also through how individuals perceive, interpret, and respond to situations in which those risks appear. This chapter examines the human factor from a communication perspective, focusing on **why individuals are targeted**, how manipulation exploits ordinary patterns of trust and urgency, why different audiences require different forms of awareness, and how organisational culture shapes security behaviour. This provides the basis for designing **awareness strategies that are realistic, targeted, and aligned** with the conditions in which people encounter cyber risk.

1.1 Why humans are targeted

People are targeted because influencing behaviour is often easier, faster, and more scalable than exploiting technical vulnerabilities. A convincing email, a request framed as urgent, or an impersonation of a trusted authority can create risk even in organisations with strong technical controls.

Many **cybersecurity incidents involve human behaviour**, including error, limited awareness, weak security practices, and susceptibility to deception (4). This does not mean that individuals should be framed simply as the “weakest link”. A communication-oriented approach recognises that people make decisions within specific organisational, social, and psychological conditions. Their responses are shaped by workload, trust, hierarchy, time pressure, internal culture, and the clarity of the information they receive.

For this reason, the human factor should be understood as both a vulnerability and a strategic point of intervention. **If attackers rely on communication to manipulate behaviour, organisations can use communication to strengthen judgement, confidence, and response.**

The motivations behind cyberattacks are diverse, ranging from financial gain and ideological objectives to power assertion, entertainment, and other forms of exploitation (8). In practice, financially motivated attacks remain among the most common within the European threat landscape (1). For communication professionals, understanding these motivations helps

explain why attacks are framed in different ways and why certain audiences are approached through specific types of messages, pressure, or requests.

The key lesson is that cybersecurity awareness must be designed around real human decision-making, with messages that are relevant to people’s roles, understandable under pressure, and practical enough to apply in daily work.

Figure 1: Threat Overview 2025

1.2 How manipulation works: human attack vectors and the mechanics of deception

Once individuals become the primary point of targeting, attackers rely on **manipulation techniques** designed around predictable patterns in human decision-making.

Social engineering is the deliberate use of psychological and communication techniques to influence a person’s behaviour in ways that serve the attacker’s objective. It works by triggering predictable patterns in how people assess trust, urgency, authority, familiarity, and risk.

Many attacks depend on how well they align with ordinary human behaviour. Techniques commonly exploit responses such as **trust in authority, sensitivity to urgency, or the**

tendency to follow established routines. Messages that appear to come from senior management, requests framed as time-critical, or communications that replicate familiar formats are more likely to be accepted without verification (10)(12).

Employees may be approached through business email compromise, citizens through public-service impersonation, managers through urgent financial requests, and organisations through supply-chain manipulation. These examples show how manipulation becomes more persuasive when it is adapted to the audience, the context, and the expected behaviour.

Time pressure plays a central role. When individuals are required to act quickly, they are more likely to rely on instinctive responses rather than deliberate evaluation (13). This increases the likelihood that urgency-based messages or simulated problems will be accepted without sufficient scrutiny. High workloads and information overload can produce similar effects by reducing the attention available for verification.

Another important factor is **contextual credibility.** Messages become more convincing when they match the recipient's role, expectations, or current activity. This alignment increases perceived legitimacy and lowers the likelihood that the interaction will be questioned.

From a communication perspective, **awareness should help users recognise how manipulation operates:** understanding why a message feels credible or urgent is an important part of recognising cyber risk before taking action

Figure 2: Tactics, techniques and procedures overview

1.3 The diversity of human targets: different audiences, different risks

People differ in how they process information, assess risk, respond to pressure, and interact with digital environments: thus cybersecurity awareness cannot be designed for a generic user. Differences influence both exposure to specific threats and the type of communication that is most likely to support safe behaviour.

Cognitive diversity is an important part of this picture. Neurodivergent individuals, including people with autism, ADHD, dyslexia, or related conditions, may process written instructions, social cues, urgency, and environmental stress differently. Awareness materials based mainly on dense text, abstract explanations, implicit cues, or fast-paced delivery may therefore fail to reach part of the intended audience (14). Clear language, structured guidance, multimodal formats, and adjustable pacing can help ensure that cybersecurity messages are understood and retained by a wider range of users.

Age also shapes both exposure to cyber threats and response to awareness communication. Older adults may be more frequently targeted by scams involving public-

service impersonation, technical support fraud, or financial deception, while younger users may be more exposed to manipulation through social media, messaging platforms, and peer-based forms of influence (1). These differences do not imply that one group is inherently more vulnerable than another; rather, they show that threat exposure and communication needs vary across audiences.

Organisational role is another decisive factor. Staff working in finance, human resources, IT, administration, senior management, or communications face different forms of targeting and operate with different levels of technical knowledge, decision-making authority, and time pressure. A finance officer receiving a payment request, an HR employee handling personal data, and a board member assessing strategic risk do not need the same message, even if they are part of the same organisation.

Figure 3: Sectorial overview

For awareness professionals, the main implication is that effective cybersecurity communication requires segmentation. Messages must be adapted to the audience’s role, knowledge level, risk exposure, and context of action. A single campaign can create visibility, but it cannot by itself build understanding across all user groups. To influence behaviour, awareness must speak to the situations people actually face.

1.4 From individual responsibility to collective security culture

Early cybersecurity communication often positioned security as primarily a matter of individual responsibility: the employee who clicks a link, uses a weak password, or fails to update software. This framing is incomplete and can be counterproductive. It overlooks the organisational conditions that shape how individuals make security-relevant decisions, including workplace pressures, leadership behaviour, internal norms, and the clarity of communication around risk (4).

A communication-oriented approach requires a **shift from blaming individual users to building a collective security culture**. Cybersecurity culture is shaped by shared values, beliefs, perceptions, attitudes, assumptions, norms, and behaviours regarding cybersecurity(13). Training sessions or isolated campaigns will not be sufficient for awareness building, which needs to be reinforced through everyday communication, consistent expectations, accessible reporting channels, and a shared understanding of why secure behaviour matters.

Leadership is central to this process. When senior leaders treat cybersecurity as a strategic priority, communicate openly about incidents without blame, and provide behaviour models expected of all staff, security culture becomes more credible and durable. When leadership is absent or disengaged, even well-designed awareness campaigns are unlikely to produce lasting behavioural change. Effective cybersecurity communication is therefore a whole-organisation effort, not only a message directed at individual employees.

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Main takeaways

- People are targeted because influencing behaviour is often easier than exploiting technical systems.
- Human responses are shaped by context, pressure, workload, trust, hierarchy, and organisational culture.
- Social engineering relies on trust, urgency, authority, familiarity, and contextual credibility.
- Different audiences experience different forms of targeting and require different communication approaches.

- Cybersecurity awareness should prepare people to question and verify when a situation feels credible but creates pressure to act.

2 Designing effective awareness campaigns

Effective cybersecurity awareness relies on communication that goes beyond information alone: structured, targeted, and aligned with how people understand and act on risk. This chapter examines the main conditions required for **awareness initiatives** to become strong communication strategies: moving beyond generic and fear-based campaigns, segmenting audiences according to their needs and contexts, addressing the specific constraints faced by SMEs, engaging leadership as a driver of organisational culture, and measuring impact to ensure that awareness efforts produce meaningful change.

2.1 The limits of generic and fear-based campaigns

Cybersecurity awareness has often relied on broad information campaigns and fear-based messaging, assuming that greater knowledge of threats will automatically lead to safer behaviour. This assumption is limited: information is necessary, but not sufficient to change behaviour. **People must understand the message**, see its relevance, feel capable of acting on it, and be motivated to apply it in their specific context. (5)

This is why one-way awareness communication often has a limited impact. Campaigns that simply distribute information about risks may increase visibility, but they do not necessarily change attitudes, intentions, or everyday security practices. In organisational settings, where users face competing priorities and different levels of technical knowledge, messages that are too general are easily ignored or treated as compliance requirements rather than practical guidance. (6)

Fear-based communication presents a similar challenge. Highlighting the seriousness of cyber threats can attract attention, but it can also produce disengagement if people feel that the problem is too complex, too distant, or beyond their control. When threat messages are

not accompanied by clear and achievable actions, the likely result is not safer behaviour but avoidance, denial, or fatigue. (15)

Effective awareness must therefore strike a **balance between communicating risk and enabling action**. Messages should explain what the threat is, why it is relevant to the audience, and what concrete action the recipient can take. This balance is particularly important in organisations where different roles, levels of expertise, and working conditions shape how people interpret and respond to cybersecurity risks.

Fear-based campaign	Balanced campaign

Figure 4: Fear-based versus balance campaigns

2.2 Audience segmentation: from mass communication to targeted intervention

Cybersecurity awareness is often delivered as a uniform message to all users, regardless of their role, experience, or exposure to risk. This approach assumes a common understanding of cybersecurity and a shared set of behaviours, which rarely reflects how organisations actually function. Security behaviours that are not aligned with users’ real working contexts are often ignored, bypassed, or treated as impractical (16).

Audience segmentation addresses this limitation by **recognising that different groups face different risks and require different forms of communication**. Employees in finance, human resources, IT, and senior management encounter distinct threat scenarios and operate under different constraints. Evidence from awareness research shows that uniform campaigns are less effective than approaches adapted to specific organisational departments and user groups (17).

Segmentation is not limited to professional roles. Factors such as levels of digital literacy, cognitive diversity, and prior experience with cybersecurity also influence how individuals interpret and respond to information. Communication that does not account for these differences risks excluding part of the audience or reducing the effectiveness of awareness efforts.

For organisations, this requires a shift from broad campaigns to targeted communication strategies. Rather than delivering the same message to everyone, awareness initiatives should **define specific audiences, identify the behaviours that need to change, and select appropriate formats and channels** to support that change. In this way, segmentation becomes a core design principle, enabling awareness efforts to move from general information provision to practical behavioural support.

WHAT DO YOU WANT TO ACHIEVE?	OBJECTIVES
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Generate awareness about cybersecurity issues and practices. 2. Raise awareness about the impact of different types of attacks, especially when they involve companies and businesses. 	<p>Awareness</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Provide detailed information on how to react in the event of phishing and ransomware attacks. 4. Inform potential attack targets of what happens before, during and after a ransomware attack. 	<p>Information</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Prompt the target audience to act and to eventually spread the word on what they learned from you. 	<p>Engagement</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Promote the safer use of the internet for end users and the practice of basic cyber hygiene. 7. Promote existing cybersecurity recommendations and best practices to prevent cyberattacks. 	<p>Promotion</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Provide users with resources to protect themselves online and prevent attacks. 9. Make people become 'human firewalls' by empowering them to play their part in preventing attacks. 	<p>Empowerment</p>

Figure 5: : [How to create your own awareness raising programmes](#)

2.3 The underserved majority: cybersecurity awareness for SMEs

Small and medium-sized enterprises face distinct challenges in implementing cybersecurity awareness. Limited resources, absence of dedicated security personnel, and reliance on external support mean that standard awareness approaches are often difficult to apply in practice. **Guidance designed for larger organisations often assumes structures, expertise, and time that SMEs do not have (2).**

In this context, cybersecurity awareness must be adapted to operational reality. Owners and employees often perform multiple roles, making it difficult to prioritise security tasks that are perceived as secondary to core business activities. Awareness communication therefore needs to be concise, directly relevant, and aligned with everyday business processes rather than presented as an additional requirement (6).

Another constraint is access to expertise. SMEs may depend on external providers or informal sources of information, which can lead to inconsistent understanding of risks and responsibilities. Clear, practical communication that translates technical concepts into actionable steps is essential to support decision-making in these environments.

Effective awareness for SMEs also depends on simplicity and applicability. Messages should focus on a limited number of priority actions that can be realistically implemented, rather than comprehensive frameworks that are difficult to operationalise. Instead of relying on standardised campaigns, communication should recognise SME constraints and support gradual, achievable improvements in cybersecurity practices.

2.4 Engaging leadership: the C-level problem

Leadership engagement is one of the conditions that determines whether cybersecurity awareness remains a training activity or becomes part of organisational culture. **When cybersecurity is delegated entirely to technical teams, it remains disconnected from strategic decision-making, organisational priorities, and business risk.** This creates a gap between the formal importance assigned to cybersecurity and the level of leadership attention required to make awareness part of organisational culture (18).

Engaging C-level audiences requires a different communication approach from that used with operational staff. Senior executives are unlikely to respond to messages framed primarily in technical terms. They need cybersecurity to be translated into business language: risk exposure, liability, continuity, regulatory responsibility, reputational impact, and organisational resilience (18).

Leadership engagement also affects the credibility of awareness efforts across the organisation. When senior leaders visibly support cybersecurity, communicate consistently about its importance, and model expected behaviours, awareness initiatives are more likely to be taken seriously. Without this involvement, campaigns risk being perceived as isolated compliance exercises rather than part of a shared organisational priority (13).

Designing communication that connects cybersecurity to executive responsibilities and organisational outcomes is essential for leadership involvement: C-level communication should therefore be concise, strategic, and focused on decisions, not only on threats or technical controls.

2.5 Measuring impact: from activity to evidence

A frequently neglected dimension of cybersecurity awareness is the evaluation of outcomes. **Organisations may invest in campaigns, training sessions, and communication materials** without defining in advance what success should look like or how it will be measured. As a result, awareness activity can become difficult to justify, even when it is well intentioned and widely delivered.

Measuring impact requires moving beyond indicators of activity, such as the number of people trained or the number of messages distributed. These figures are useful, but they do not show whether awareness has changed knowledge, attitudes, or behaviour. Effective evaluation should therefore consider reach, knowledge improvement, attitude change, and observable security behaviour (19).

This also means that measurement should be built into awareness design from the beginning. Pre- and post-training assessments, phishing simulations, reporting rates, staff surveys, and qualitative feedback can all help organisations understand whether communication is producing the intended effect. Evaluation should therefore serve accountability, but also continuous improvement.

Evidence-based awareness depends on **learning from results and adapting communication accordingly**. If a campaign does not produce the expected change, the response should not be simply to repeat the same message more often, but to review the audience, format, channel, and call to action. In this way, measurement becomes part of the communication process itself, helping organisations move from awareness activity to demonstrable impact.

Main takeaways

- Awareness needs clear objectives, defined audiences, and actions people can easily implement.

- Generic and fear-based campaigns lose impact when messages feel distant or overwhelming.
- Segmentation makes awareness more relevant to different roles, expertise levels, and contexts.
- SMEs need practical guidance that reflects limited resources and operational constraints.
- Leadership increases the credibility and long-term impact of awareness.
- Measurement shows whether awareness is changing knowledge, attitudes, and behaviour.

3 Making cybersecurity engaging

Creative and participatory approaches are becoming increasingly important as they address one of the central limitations of traditional awareness communication: information alone does not necessarily produce attention, retention, or behaviour change. This chapter examines how **engaging formats can strengthen cybersecurity communication** by making risks

clearer, more concrete, and easier to connect to real situations. It focuses on the cognitive foundations of engagement, the use of gamification and storytelling, the importance of collective and team-based formats, and the practical factors that should guide the selection of awareness methods in different organisational contexts.

3.1 The cognitive case for engagement

The way cybersecurity information is presented influences whether people remember it, understand its relevance, and apply it in practice. Awareness formats that involve participation, discussion, or problem-solving tend to support stronger retention than passive instruction because they require users to engage actively with the information rather than simply receive it (20).

Engaging formats can also strengthen motivation and involvement. Gamified training approaches, for example, can encourage more sustained participation by giving users a better sense of involvement, competence, and autonomy rather than relying primarily on obligation or compliance pressure (21). This is particularly important in cybersecurity awareness, where secure behaviour often depends on attention, judgement, and repeated decision-making in everyday contexts.

Research on gamification within cybersecurity awareness programmes reports positive effects on engagement, knowledge retention, and behavioural outcomes within both public and private sector environments (22). At the same time, the literature also shows that gamification does not automatically produce effective learning outcomes. Its impact depends on the quality of the design and on how well the format is aligned with the intended audience, communication objective and organisational context.

3.2 Gamification in practice: from escape rooms to serious games

The practical landscape of gamified cybersecurity awareness encompasses a wide range of formats, each associated with different learning objectives and forms of participation.

Escape rooms represent one of the most documented creative formats in cybersecurity education. Participants are placed in a simulated scenario, often linked to an organisational security incident, where they must collaborate to identify threats, solve challenges, and make decisions within a limited timeframe. This type of immersive and collaborative activity

combines multiple learning mechanisms simultaneously, including problem-solving, communication under pressure, and applied decision-making. Studies on cybersecurity escape rooms have found that scenario-based learning significantly improves engagement and helps participants connect abstract cybersecurity concepts to realistic and role-specific situations (23)(24).

Red Team / Blue Team exercises provide a different type of experiential learning. In these activities, one group simulates attackers while another responds as defenders, reproducing the dynamics of real attack-and-response situations. These exercises help participants understand how attacks unfold, how defensive decisions are made, and how communication failures can contribute to security incidents (21).

Serious games and video games extend gamification toward sustained and self-directed learning. These formats allow participants to engage with cybersecurity concepts progressively across multiple sessions, revisit difficult scenarios, and practise responses in low-risk environments. Game-based formats can be particularly useful for audiences less responsive to conventional training, because they allow users to practise cybersecurity decisions through repeated, interactive scenarios rather than one-off instruction (25).

European-level initiatives also provide **practical examples of how game-based awareness can be used..** [ENISA's "AR-in-a-Box Game](#), offers an awareness-raising activity designed to help any audience self-evaluate its awareness level against common cyber threats after receiving basic cyber awareness training. Participants solve a riddle by answering questions, allowing the activity to combine learning, participation, and self-assessment. The game forms part of **ENISA's wider AR-in-a-Box solution**,(26) which provides theoretical and practical knowledge on how to design and implement cybersecurity awareness programmes for public bodies, operators of essential services, and both large and small private companies

3.3 Storytelling as a communication tool

Alongside gamification, storytelling represents another engagement-based approach to cybersecurity communication. **Narrative formats** can make cybersecurity risks more concrete by linking technical threats to human experiences, decisions, and consequences.

Research on narrative persuasion demonstrates that individuals who become cognitively and emotionally immersed in a story are more likely to accept narrative-consistent beliefs and retain the associated message over time (27).

Storytelling can take multiple forms, including victim narratives, fictional scenarios, reconstructed incident timelines, and organisational case studies. These approaches allow audiences to explore risky situations in a safe environment while understanding how incidents develop and how responses unfold. Storytelling helps audiences connect cybersecurity concepts to concrete situations, making it easier to understand how secure or insecure behaviour manifest themselves (28).

Narrative formats also offer practical advantages. They humanise cyber threats, support identification with realistic situations, and can be adapted to a wide range of communication channels without requiring extensive technical infrastructure.

Figure 6: Tips for Avoiding Cyber Manipulation

3.4 Collective formats and the social dimension of security culture

A recurring theme across both the gamification and storytelling literature is the importance of collective experience in cybersecurity awareness. Durable behavioural

change is more likely to emerge through shared norms, social interaction, and collective learning processes than through isolated individual instruction (29).

Team-based awareness activities create opportunities for participants to develop shared understandings of risk, establish common expectations around secure behaviour, and reinforce organisational norms collectively. Workshops, role-playing activities, collaborative exercises, and group simulations allow participants not only to learn individually, but also to practice communication, coordination, and decision-making within a team environment.

The social dimension of awareness also extends to relationships between employees and security teams. Research indicates that direct interaction and familiarity between users and security professionals can significantly strengthen trust, reporting behaviour, and long-term engagement with cybersecurity practices (6).

Creative awareness formats work best when they are integrated into wider awareness strategies. Their effectiveness often depends on the shared experiences, social reinforcement, and organisational discussions they generate.

3.5 Selecting the right format: a practical framework

The increasing diversity of cybersecurity awareness formats creates a practical selection challenge for organisations. Different formats support different objectives, audiences, and organisational constraints, meaning that no single approach is universally appropriate.

Several dimensions should guide format selection. **The first is audience characteristics**, including technical literacy, age profile, neurodiversity, and motivational drivers. Different audiences will respond differently to the same awareness method.

The second dimension to consider is the **learning objective**. Escape rooms, storytelling, phishing simulations, workshops, and video games each support different

forms of learning, ranging from emotional engagement and threat recognition to behavioural practice and collective coordination.

The third consideration is **resource and infrastructure constraints**. Some formats require dedicated facilitation, technical infrastructure, or specialised expertise, while others can be implemented more flexibly with large audiences.

The fourth consideration to take into account is **measurement alignment**. Awareness formats should support measurable outcomes that correspond to the organisation's evaluation framework, including behavioural indicators, participation patterns, or qualitative feedback.

Current research highlights the absence of standardised criteria for selecting awareness formats within different contexts (25)(22). In practice, the most effective approach is often a portfolio model in which organisations combine multiple formats adapted to different audiences, learning objectives, and operational realities.

Main takeaways

- Participation and interaction strengthen attention, retention, and behavioural engagement.
- Gamification helps users practise cybersecurity decisions through active and repeated involvement.
- Storytelling makes cyber risks easier to connect to real situations and human experiences.
- Team-based formats strengthen shared responsibility, communication, and security culture.
- Different awareness formats support different audiences, objectives, and organisational contexts.
- Effective format selection depends on audience needs, learning goals, available resources, and measurement objectives.

Conclusions

This white paper has argued that cybersecurity depends on the interaction between technology, people, and communication. Technical measures provide essential protection, while effective awareness helps people understand risks, recognise their role, and act with confidence in the situations where cyber threats emerge. For this reason, awareness should be designed as a strategic communication function: audience-focused, behaviour-oriented, and grounded in the real contexts in which cyber risk appears.

The policy gap and its implications

The European Union has developed an increasingly strong cybersecurity framework through initiatives such as the NIS2 Directive and the EU Cybersecurity Act. These measures recognise that cybersecurity resilience depends on both technical and human factors. However, policy alone does not produce behavioural change.

As ENISA's NIS Investments 2024 report shows, investment continues to focus more heavily on technology than on people, while awareness and staffing gaps remain visible across several sectors (2). Regulatory frameworks can require organisations to implement awareness programmes, but they cannot guarantee that those programmes are effective, relevant to their audience, or capable of producing long-term behavioural change (29).

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Recommendations

Several recommendations emerge from the analysis presented in this white paper.

Cybersecurity awareness should adopt an audience-first approach. Different audiences face different risks, levels of expertise, and operational pressures, meaning that generic campaigns are rarely sufficient.

Awareness should focus on empowerment rather than fear. Communication is more effective when people understand what action they can take, rather than being overwhelmed by abstract or high-pressure threat messaging (15).

Leadership engagement should be treated as a core condition for organisational culture change. Awareness initiatives are more credible and more sustainable when cybersecurity is visibly supported at management level.

SMEs require greater attention within the European cybersecurity ecosystem. Smaller organisations often lack dedicated expertise and resources, making accessible and practical awareness support especially important.

Creative and participatory formats should be treated as legitimate awareness tools rather than optional additions. Gamification, storytelling, and team-based learning can strengthen engagement, retention, and practical understanding when they are well designed and aligned with communication objectives (21)(22).

Awareness programmes should be evaluated systematically. Measurement allows organisations to understand what works, improve communication strategies over time, and demonstrate the value of awareness investment.

The recommendations outlined above point to the need for stronger exchange between the organisations and communities working on cybersecurity awareness in Europe. This is where COcyber can make a practical contribution.

By bringing together civilian and defence cybersecurity actors, COcyber supports dialogue, knowledge-sharing, and comparison of approaches within different contexts. This role is closely aligned with the central argument of this White Paper: cybersecurity culture is strengthened through sustained collaboration, shared learning, and communication adapted to real audiences and operational realities.

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